

MEDICAL SCIENCES

BENIGN MULTICYSTIC PERITONEAL MESOTHELIOMA

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ABSTRACT

Benign multicystic mesothelioma of the peritoneum is a rare benign tumor that, unlike pleural mesothelial neoplasms, is not associated with asbestos exposure. The etiology and pathogenesis of multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma are unclear, although associations with some inflammatory and other pathological processes have been established. The diagnosis of this tumor is postoperative because it requires morphological verification due to the multiple cystic formations in the abdominal cavity with a similar macroscopic appearance.

We present a case of peritoneal localization of benign multicystic mesothelioma in a 79-year-old patient. The tumor measured 8/4/3 cm and was attached to the serosa of the small intestine. Its clinical manifestation was in the form of ileus, which necessitated urgent surgical intervention with removal of the formation.

The most common differential diagnostic options for similar cystic processes in the abdominal cavity are discussed, as well as the grounds for making this diagnosis from a morphological and biological point of view, despite the WHO recommendations for changing the nomenclature.

Keywords: benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma, peritoneal inclusion cyst, echinococcal cyst, pneumatosis cystoides intestinalis.

Introduction

Benign cystic mesothelioma, also called multicystic mesothelioma, is a rare tumor that is difficult to diagnose preoperatively, is more common in women, and is not associated with asbestosis, unlike mesothelial lesions of the pleura. Macroscopically, the tumor presents as a single-chamber or multi-chamber cyst, with smooth walls lined with mesothelial cells. Its cavity is filled with translucent fluid. The sizes of cystic mesotheliomas vary from 0.1 cm in diameter to over 30 cm in multi-chamber cystic formations [7, 8].

The pathogenesis of this benign tumor process is unclear. Various inflammatory and neoplastic factors are discussed for its occurrence. In women, it is often associated with endometriosis and inflammatory processes in the pelvic organs. WHO recommends the terminology peritoneal inclusion cysts instead of benign (multi) cystic mesothelioma. According to ICD-10 coding, the nomenclature of the process is Benign neoplasm of mesothelial tissue of peritoneum.

Case report

From the anamnesis: A 79-year-old man was admitted to the Surgical Department of Devin Hospital with severe abdominal pain and bloating, persistent vomiting, lack of gas and defecation for one day.

Clinical data: Due to the established clinical symptoms of intestinal obstruction (ileus), an exploratory laparotomy was performed. Intraoperatively, a multi-chamber cystic formation measuring 8/4/3 cm was found. It has a smooth, large-lobulated outer surface, soft-elastic consistency, fused with the serosa of the jejunum (Fig.1). In order to preserve the integrity of the intestinal wall, also considering the benign cystic appearance of the formation, as well as the patient's chronic concomitant diseases, a sparing partial excision of the pathological process was performed. The material was sent for biopsy examination.

Fig. 1. Multicystic formation attached to the wall of a small intestinal loop

Material and methods

The histological specimens were made with fixative in 10% neutral formaldehyde (formalin) and embedded in paraffin. Sections were made with a thickness of 4 μ m and stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin (HE).

Results of microscopic examination

Fragments of fibrous wall of a multi-chamber cyst lined by benign mesothelial cells (Fig.2). It occurs in areas with mesothelial proliferations. The morphological finding is consistent with benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma (peritoneal mesothelial inclusion cyst). According to WHO guidelines, a complete resection is recommended.

Fig. 2. Fibrous wall of a multi-chamber cystic formation, lined mainly by single-layer mesothelium, stained with HE, magn. X 100.

Fig. 3. Wall of a peritoneal cyst formation, with focal mesothelial proliferations, stained with HE, magn. x 400.

Discussion

Benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma is a rare tumor that occurs most often in women of reproductive age. The tumors can be multifocal or unilocular and are usually diagnosed only when they have reached a relatively large size [8]. Morphologically, the mesothelial cells lining the cysts vary from flattened to cuboidal. The cysts are thin-walled and often contain eosinophilic fluid. In some areas, their lining may also contain foci of mesothelial hyperplasia [4]. According to the WHO, the treatment of benign cystic mesothelioma should be complete surgical resection. The WHO also considers that patient follow-up is necessary, since it has been established that 50% of tumors recur after excision [7]. At the same time, these recommendations contradict another position of the WHO - to use the diagnostic category of inclusion peritoneal cyst. Benign cystic formations do not have the characteristics of tumor processes and are not classified as such because they lack the typical biological behavior of a tumor. What is the WHO's reason for this change in the name of the process remains unclear. In support of a tumor process is also the high frequency of recurrences (50%), which in turn raises the question of how benign the behavior of the tumor is.

The differential diagnosis of benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma includes various pathological processes in the abdominal and pelvic cavities - lymphangiomas, with cystic dilatation, containing chylous fluid (especially in young patients), local ascites around small intestinal loops, pneumatosis cystoides intestinalis, echinococcal cysts. In women, a wide range of gynecological diseases should also be considered - from ovarian cystic formations (including cystic teratomas) to cystic endosalpingiosis [1].

Pneumatosis cystoides intestinalis is a rare pathological process characterized by the presence of multiple gas-filled cysts in the submucosa or subserosa of the intestinal wall. Rupture of some cysts leads to pneu-

moperitoneum, which in the absence of an inflammatory process is not followed by the development of peritonitis. The condition is often an incidental finding in patients aged between 50-80 years and on imaging studies presents as asymptomatic bubbles on the intestinal wall [2, 3].

Although the incidence of cystic echinococcosis in Bulgaria is showing a downward trend (to 1.37‰, 2020), this disease is still of important medical and social importance for the country. In cases of abdominal pain and a CT scan of the abdomen, which reveals the presence of cystic formations, it is appropriate to consider echinococcosis in the differential diagnosis, the diagnosis of which can be confirmed by a positive serological result for echinococcosis by ELISA [5]. The rare organ localization of echinococcal cysts practically includes almost all organs, except the liver and lungs, where they are most often found. Cases of echinococcal cysts in the heart, CNS, skeletal muscles, mammary gland, spleen, retroperitoneum and other rare localizations have been observed, in which delayed etiological focus and clinical complications have been found. In these cases, timely qualified parasitological diagnostics, postoperative antiparasitic treatment and dispensary observation are of essential importance for adequate therapeutic behavior [5, 6]

Conclusion

Clinically diagnosed cystic masses in the abdominal cavity require a broad differential diagnosis and a multidisciplinary approach. In these cases, benign multicystic peritoneal mesothelioma should also be considered.

References

1. Alvir I. et al., Benign Multicystic Peritoneal Mesothelioma Mimicking Gynecologic Pathology, *Acta Clin. Croat.* 2021, Jun; 60 (2): 323-325.
2. Jandu J. et al. Case Report: Pneumatosis Cystoides Intestinalis, *Rheumatologist*, November 2023.

3. Pata F. and Di Sverio S., The New England Journal of Medicine, Pneumatois Cystoides intestinalis with pneumoperitoneum, 2019, Vol. 380, No 13.
4. Pitta X. et al., Bening multisystic peritoneal mesothelioma: a case report, Med. Case Rep. 2010, Nov 29:4:385.
5. Popova G., Vutchev D., Eneva K., Masarlieva A., Familial Cystic Echinococcosis (A Case Report), IX National Conference HIV/AIDS in the pandemic Covid-19. Exotic Infectious And Parasit Diseases Collection of articles, ISBN 978-619-237-101-2 (2022) pp. 152-156.
6. Vuchev D., Masarlieva A., Bozhkov M., Rusinova Al., Eneva K., Sheitanova N., Human echinococcosis in rare organ localization, Seventh National Conference on Infectious Diseases, 2012, 59-62.
7. www.pathologyoutlines.com/caseof-week/case205.htm
8. www.pathologyoutlines.com/topic/pleura-peritmulticysticmeso.html